

Tool for Metadata Extraction and Content Packaging as Endorsed in OAIS Framework

Payal Abichandani, Rishi Prakash, Paras Nath Barwal, B. K. Murthy

Abstract—Information generated from various computerization processes is a potential rich source of knowledge for its designated community. To pass this information from generation to generation without modifying the meaning is a challenging activity. To preserve and archive the data for future generations it's very essential to prove the authenticity of the data. It can be achieved by extracting the metadata from the data which can prove the authenticity and create trust on the archived data. Subsequent challenge is the technology obsolescence. Metadata extraction and standardization can be effectively used to resolve and tackle this problem. Metadata can be categorized at two levels i.e. Technical and Domain level broadly. Technical metadata will provide the information that can be used to understand and interpret the data record, but only this level of metadata isn't sufficient to create trustworthiness. We have developed a tool which will extract and standardize the technical as well as domain level metadata. This paper is about the different features of the tool and how we have developed this.

Keyword—Digital Preservation, Metadata, OAIS, PDI, XML.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS paper is about that how the critical assets of the Indian legal system can be organized for long term digital preservation with the help of software tool called *Disposed Case Portfolio Manager (DCPM)*. This software is based on Open Archival Information System (OAIS: ISO 14721 standard) framework [1] developed by NASA's Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) [2].

There are about millions of cases disposed by Indian courts per year and each court is maintaining their data independently in different ways. The first step is to collect the data from distributed architecture [3], [4]. After that, the metadata extraction and standardization along with its data is another critical and essential activity. DCPM tool will collect the data from NIC system followed by the process of metadata extraction and standardization [5], [6].

One of the key features of this tool is that, it will classify the metadata into two categories, that is, *Descriptive metadata and Representation Information*.

II. DCPM ARCHITECTURE

This tool will be deployed in Delhi courts to collect the Disposed Case records.

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Fig. 1 Disposed Case Portfolio manager Architecture (DCPM)

There are three major processes of DCPM:

1. Data Collection
2. Metadata Generation and Standardization
3. Packet Creation for Long Term Preservation.

III. DATA COLLECTION

Data collection will be done at producer level. Data collection can be a fully/semi-automatic procedure depends upon the situation. In this pilot project CDAC has developed a procedure to fetch the data from the NIC database and will also have the option to upload the disposed cases files into the DCPM software. During the upload activity of individual documents it's very essential to maintain the indexing of these documents. The indexing feature in DCPM is dynamic i.e. each respective court can maintain the order of placement of documents as per their standard. This tool is also maintaining the type of documents which needs to be uploaded.

Descriptive Metadata - In this direction, CDAC Noida had developed a Metadata Standards for Long Term Digital preservation of Disposed Case Records. This standard has been made mandatory for Delhi courts under National Digital Preservation Program. Presently each court is maintaining their records in different manners and there are about millions of cases which need to be standardized per court. This challenge has been catered by DCPM tool. It will collect the data from NIC database for all Delhi courts as per the respective configuration and after collecting the data it will extract and standardize the metadata as per the above mentioned standard.

Representation Information is used to interpret and understand the data. In this evolving era, technology is changing every day and the data with specific technology can be interpreted with the help of its technical metadata only e.g.

if record is available in .pdf format then pdf version number, software configuration etc. is required to render and interpret the stored record.

IV. METADATA GENERATION

In the metadata extraction phase DCPM will separate the domain and technical metadata. The domain metadata will be segregated into different sections as per the standard. For technical metadata the Representation Information will be extracted from each record. All the extracted metadata will be stored in the open source format. In case of domain metadata, there will be provision in the software to manually enter the missing metadata as per the access rights.

Once the data collection and metadata generation is complete, next step is to standardize the metadata.

V. PACKET CREATION

CDAC has developed a standard folder structure for keeping the packets termed as Submission Information Package. This packet will consist of data and its standardized metadata along with packing information.

Following are the components of the packet:

1. Data- It will contain the digitized document and media files.
2. Metadata- It will have the domain and technical metadata for each and every file.
3. Manifest File- It will contain the packaging information about the data and its metadata. This information will be useful for secure packet travelling and packet validation.
4. PDI file

VI. SIP ARCHITECTURE

Submission Information Package is one of the components of OAIS information. SIP is a collection of data and its metadata along with preservation information. The main goal of DCPM is to produce SIP packets at producer level which can be later on transferred to the central location for long term digital preservation. Therefore, we have to standardize a SIP structure, so that later on it can be converted into an Archival Information Package for long term storage.

- XML

Fig. 2 SIP Packet Architecture

SIP is basically a combination of data and its metadata. Therefore, to preserve the case record it is essential to extract the metadata from every document and encode it into an open

source format. For each case record there will be single domain file, which will contain the domain level metadata filled/finalized by expertise. To make SIP more secure and to maintain the transaction details, packet will be enclosed by the manifest file.

VII. RESULT

A SIP packet in the above defined structure architecture will be the result for each and every disposed off case. There must be four types of XML file in each SIP packet.

A. Manifest File

Manifest file [7] will contain the transactions details of SIP packet, such as, sender and receiver's details, path and checksum of all file folders.

Sample File is:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<Manifest>
  <SIPInformation>
    <SIPId>3100250000032015</SIPId>
    <CaseId>024020000021980</CaseId>
    <SIPSourceInfo>Disposed Case Portfolio Manager V1.6</SIPSourceInfo>
    <SIPPackageInfo>As per the metadata standard V1.7</SIPPackageInfo>
    <SIPFormat>.tar</SIPFormat>
  </SIPInformation>
  <DataFolder>
    <Path>/3100250000032015/DATA/</Path>
    <Size>233512242</Size>
    <Checksum>c665d4aa9800162b4604738c3ad4904bbf15a9712f8c905ed2e</Checksum>
    <ChecksumAlgorithm>MD5</ChecksumAlgorithm>
  </DataFolder>
  <DataFolderStructure>
    <ChecksumAlgorithm>SHA1</ChecksumAlgorithm>
  </DataFolderStructure>
  <CreatedBy>
    <Name>kkd_validator</Name>
    <Role>Validator</Role>
  </CreatedBy>
  <SystemInformation>
    <ServerIpAddress>/10.226.19.34</ServerIpAddress>
    <ServerMACAddress>FC-4D-D4-39-22-18</ServerMACAddress>
    <ClientIpAddress>0:0:0:0:0:1</ClientIpAddress>
    <ClientMACAddress/>
  </SystemInformation>
  <OrganisationName>Near Laxmi Nagar</OrganisationName>
  <OrganisationAddress>Delhi</OrganisationAddress>
  <PhysicalFileRecordRoomNumber>50</PhysicalFileRecordRoomNumber>
  <FileIdentificationTag/>
  <CreatedFor>Near Laxmi Nagar</CreatedFor>
  <TimeStamp>
    <Date format="dd/MM/yyyy">25/06/2015</Date>
    <Time format="HH:mm:ss">12:41:37 IST</Time>
  </TimeStamp>
  <CreatedFor>Near Laxmi Nagar</CreatedFor>
  <SenderDetails>
    <SenderName>kkd_validator</SenderName>
    <SenderRole>Validator</SenderRole>
    <SenderIpAddress>0:0:0:0:0:1</SenderIpAddress>
    <SenderMACAddress/>
    <OrganisationName>Near Laxmi Nagar</OrganisationName>
    <OrganisationAddress>Delhi</OrganisationAddress>
  </SenderDetails>
</Manifest>
```

Fig. 3 Sample Manifest File

B. Provenance Description Information (PDI) File

PDI [8], [9] XML file will contain provenance information of the packet, as from where this comes, from which machine this packet is generated. Access right information will also goes in this file.

Sample PDI file is:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<PreservationDescriptionInformation>
  <ReferenceInformation>
    <SIPId>3100250000032015</SIPId>
    <BatchId/>
    <Format>.tar</Format>
    <EncodingStandard>UTF-8</EncodingStandard>
    <SIPSourceInfo>Disposed Case Portfolio Manager V1.6</SIPSourceInfo>
    <SIPPackageInfo>As per the metadata standard V1.7</SIPPackageInfo>
  </ReferenceInformation>
  <ProvenanceInformation>
    <Origin>
      <Name>kkd_validator</Name>
      <SIPCreationDate>25/06/2015, 12:41:41 IST</SIPCreationDate>
    </Origin>
    <SystemInformation>
      <ServerIpAddress>/10.226.19.34</ServerIpAddress>
      <ServerMACAddress>FC-4D-D4-39-22-18</ServerMACAddress>
      <ClientIpAddress>0:0:0:0:0:1</ClientIpAddress>
      <ClientMACAddress/>
    </SystemInformation>
    <CourtRoomNumber>50</CourtRoomNumber>
    <CourtComplexID>Near Laxmi Nagar Delhi Delhi 110001 India</CourtComplexID>
  </SystemInformation>
  <Ingestor>
  </Ingestor>
  <Receiver/>
  <AccessRightInformation>
    <permission>public</permission>
    <CopyRightInfo>Karkardooma Court</CopyRightInfo>
    <LicenseInfo>012543</LicenseInfo>
    <LegalFramework>KKD</LegalFramework>
    <RecordHoldingAgency>IT Dept KKD court</RecordHoldingAgency>
  </AccessRightInformation>
  <ProvenanceInformation>
  </ProvenanceInformation>
  <ContextInformation>
  </ContextInformation>
  <FixityInformation>
    <Checksum>SHA1</Checksum>
    <ChecksumInfo>256 bit compression</ChecksumInfo>
  </FixityInformation>
</PreservationDescriptionInformation>
```

Fig. 4 Sample PDI File

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He was awarded Ph.D. degree by IIT Delhi. He is instrumental in the initiation of e-learning activities and contributed for the incorporation of Media Lab Asia. He also served as Executive Director, NIELIT (erstwhile DOEACC). He was a member of Technical Committee & Project Approval Board of National Mission on Education through ICT (NMEICT), MHRD; Academic Advisory Committee, School of Computer Sciences, IGNOU.

Dr. Murthy's research interests include Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Processing, Knowledge Engineering, Object Oriented Design and Semantic Web. He has published and presented more than 45 papers in various journals and conferences.

Payal Abichandani is working as a Sr. Technical Officer in C-DAC NOIDA. She has done her engineering in Computer Science and MBA in Operations Management. She is leading the development activity of the Project called as "Center of Excellence for Digital Preservation" under National Digital Preservation Program.

She is also leading other projects as well which is under DeitY-"Department of Electronics and Information Technology", such as, M-SIPS and ICMR. She has worked on metadata standards required for the long-term digital preservation of disposed case records. In the Conference "e-Court Present and Future" held on July 2012, she presented the metadata standards required for the digital preservation of Judiciary records. She joined CDAC in 2011. Previously she was associated with AVL India Software Pvt. Ltd. from Automobile Industry Her total experience is 8yrs. The Project handled by her in AVL was used to test the engine performance of automobiles called as EDACS. Her expertise is System Analysis, Architecture Design and Implementation.

Rishi Prakash received his B.E in Instrumentation and Control from NSIT (Netaji Subhash Institute of Technology) Delhi University. He has joined C-DAC Noida in early 2000 and has worked with embedded system and e-Governance division.

He has completed the "e-Court" pilot project which established a "proof of concept" of development of software for search, archive of records and writing depositions in local language along with setting up video recording and video conferencing inside the courtroom.

This is very novel and prestigious project implemented at City civil and Sessions Court, Ahmadabad, under the guidance of High Court of Gujarat and has the honor of having implemented for the first time India. The same project was awarded with "Gold Medal" in 13th National e-Governance conference held in 18-19th Feb 2010 Jaipur. Currently he is working as a chief-investigator for Digital Preservation of Case Records project under National Digital Preservation program funded by DeitY, MCIT, Govt. of India.

Paras Nath Barwal received his M.Tech in Computer Science from BIT (Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra, Ranchi). He has joined CDAC, Noida in Feb 2001. Currently he is Joint Director and Group-coordinator of e-Governance group in CDAC-Noida.

He was Project Manager for Design Development of various e-Governance projects like executing setting up of RTC (Rural Tele Centers) in Lao PDR under Lao PDR and India ICT Bilateral Co-operation ,ITAS for Northern Railways, BIS, DeitY, MCD, TRAI, LMIS for DDA, DTL, IPGCL, Forensic Science Laboratory (FSL), Decision Support System (DSS), IPO.

Dr. B.K Murthy is currently holding the charge of Executive Director, C-DAC, Noida Centre, on deputation from DeitY, MCIT, Govt of India. As the Head of the Noida Centre of C-DAC, he is responsible for policy formulation, planning, implementation and deployment of various R&D Projects.

In his capacity as Senior Director, DeitY he was responsible for the National Knowledge Network, Human Resources